

MDMC

Master in Data Management
and Curation

MASTER IN DATA MANAGEMENT AND
CURATION

Design refinement and
commissioning of a
FAIR-by-design integrated data
management system for an STM
laboratory

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Author's Declaration

I, VIGNERI STEFANO, declare that this thesis entitled, 'Design refinement and commissioning of a FAIR-by-design integrated data management system for an STM laboratory' and the work presented therein are my own.

I certify that:

- This work was performed wholly or principally during MDMC internship in the STRAS laboratory, CNR-IOM, Trieste, Italy.
- If any part of this thesis has previously been submitted for a degree or any other qualification at this University or any other institution, this has been clearly stated.
- Where I have relied on the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed.
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Abstract

In recent years, the ever-growing volume and complexity of scientific data have made traditional data management practices inadequate. To address this issue, a new set of guiding principles for data management has emerged, asserting that high-quality research data must be F.A.I.R. — Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. This thesis initiates the adoption of FAIR practices in the STRAS laboratory at CNR-IOM in Trieste, Italy, specifically focusing on data produced through Scanning Tunnelling Microscopy (STM).

Several solutions were developed to support the FAIR data transition. A workflow was designed within the electronic laboratory notebook eLabFTW to improve the organization, annotation, and traceability of research meta-data. Additionally, a Python-based graphical user interface, named Meerkat, was created to assist researchers in preliminarily processing STM data, automating (meta)data management in eLabFTW, and visualising STM data. To ensure interoperability of the experimental data, STM output files were mapped onto the NXstm schema proposed by FAIRmat and prepared for conversion into the NeXus format, in order to facilitate their subsequent upload to the NOMAD data management platform.

Despite the goals achieved during this thesis, the FAIR-ification process at STRAS remains ongoing. This work lays the basis for embedding FAIR principles into the laboratory's daily practices, enabling more open, reproducible, and efficient scientific research.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Up to today, scientific research has produced a vast amount of data in various types (e.g., numeric data or strings), formats, and originating from different scientific techniques. Due to ongoing scientific progress, along with the rise of machine learning and artificial intelligence (AI), this already large quantity of data is expected to increase. Consequently, its relevance in driving scientific progress, and the necessity for producing and accessing high-quality data, are also expected to grow.

Despite that, previous generations of researchers did not always manage the data they produced and published in the best or most correct manner. Data and corresponding metadata — that is, other data describing and providing information about the data — have often been collected inaccurately, in a non-standardized manner, not always using the same vocabulary, in ways that are not easily interpretable except by the data’s author, and with tools that do not support long-term storage or the capability to be read by machines — such as paper-based laboratory notebooks.

This behaviour hinders experiments’ *repeatability* and *reproducibility*, which are respectively the ability to obtain consistent results when an experiment is repeated exactly under the same conditions — e.g., same operator, instrument, and measuring conditions — and the ability to obtain consistent results when an experiment is reproduced under different conditions, such as different observers, measuring instruments, or locations. Moreover, it limits the shareability of data with other users — both humans and machines — interested in utilising it. This last aspect, data sharing, is of fundamental importance to ensure that all the information contained within data can be fully exploited, and to automate and accelerate scientific research.

Therefore, the behaviour of the past is no longer sustainable in a data-driven society like ours, and new practices and tools must be adopted to enable adequate data management — in particular, making data and metadata

Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable — in one word: *F.A.I.R.*

The scientific research *FAIR-ification* must encompass the entire scientific process, starting from research project planning to the production, processing, sharing, and publication of research data — meaning, making scientific research and its results *FAIR-by-design*.

The work done during this thesis is situated within this context. In particular, the pilot training course *Master in Data Management and Curation* (MDMC) — organised by *Area Science Park* [1], *CNR-IOM* [2], and *SISSA* [3] — aims to train a new professional in the field of scientific research: the data curator or data steward. Their role is to guide researchers in laboratories toward a more responsible and appropriate management of the data they use.

The MDMC is supported by two PNRR (*Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza*) projects: NFFA-DI (*Nano Foundries and Fine Analysis – Digital Infrastructure*) [4], and PRP@CERIC (*Pathogen Readiness Platform for CERIC-ERIC upgrade*) [5].

In particular, this thesis was conducted at the STRAS laboratory at CNR-IOM in Trieste (Italy) — one of the operational units within the NFFA-DI project — and its aim aligns with one of the project’s broader goals: enabling operational units (in this case, limited to the STRAS laboratory) to produce FAIR data that can subsequently be uploaded to the project’s datalake, named OFED (*Overarching FAIR Ecosystem for Data*), specifically onto a local installation of the materials science data management platform *NOMAD*. Throughout the remainder of the thesis, when referring to uploading data to NOMAD in the context of the NFFA-DI project, this local installation will be implied.

The following chapters introduce the guidelines of the FAIR data principles and present several tools that can be utilised in the FAIR data context. They then introduce the STRAS laboratory and one of the experimental techniques available there — *Scanning Tunnelling Microscopy* (STM) — whose data must be made FAIR. Specifically, the typical STRAS experimental workflow is described, as understanding this workflow is crucial to identifying the real needs of the researchers and initiating a meaningful FAIR-ification process that can be effectively implemented in synergy with them.

Finally, the chapters present and discuss several solutions — designed and implemented during this thesis — to make the laboratory more FAIR-data-compliant, and in particular, FAIR-by-design. Specifically, they cover the proper use of an electronic laboratory notebook, the development of a Python-based *graphical user interface* (GUI) to automate and standardise the execution of certain researcher tasks, and the mapping of STM data generated at STRAS into a specific schema for conversion into a format

more suitable for upload to NOMAD.

Chapter 2

FAIR data context and tools

With the advancement of technological and scientific progress, an increasing amount of data and metadata has been generated by research infrastructures. This has created a need for appropriate practices and tools to manage this information in a way that ensures it can be safely and long-term stored, as well as easily shared and understood by both humans and machines. This need has led to the affirmation of the *FAIR data* concept.

First of all, this chapter will introduce and discuss the *FAIR data guiding principles*. Then, it will present several useful tools to support their implementation: the open-source *HDF5* file format and the *NeXus* data format built on top of it for research data storage; a platform for materials science data management (*NOMAD*); and finally, an electronic laboratory notebook for storing researcher-generated data (*eLabFTW*).

2.1 FAIR data principles

The idea of defining a minimal set of guiding principles and good practices to discover, access, integrate, reuse, and cite, in an easy and appropriate manner, the huge amount of information being generated in science dates back to the "Jointly Designing a Data Fairport" workshop held in Leiden, the Netherlands, in 2014 [6]. During the workshop, a large number of academic and private stakeholders in the scientific data landscape met and produced a draft of a set of foundational principles, subsequently improved, and to date known as *FAIR Guiding Principles*.

The term FAIR is an acronym for *Findable*, *Accessible*, *Interoperable*, and *Reusable*. These are four attributes that not only scientific data and metadata, but all the scientific research outcomes should have in order to be appropriately re-used by all stakeholders (e.g., researchers, professional

data publishers, software and tool builders, funding agencies, data scientists) — even, and especially, when they are accessed through machines (e.g., applications and computational agents). To date, indeed, the employment of machines to automatically find and use research data is gaining more and more relevance, hence it is fundamental to enable them to correctly process all this information.

In the FAIR context, "Findable" means that all the digital resources (e.g., data and metadata) should be easy to be found by either humans or machines. Hence, machine-readable metadata are an essential part of the *FAIRification* process, indeed they are fundamental for the automatic discovery of relevant datasets and services. "Accessible" means that it should be made explicit and clear to both humans and machines how they can have access and retrieve the digital resources, including authorization and authentication protocols. "Interoperable" means that it should be made possible for machines to integrate data with other data, moreover it should be possible to exchange data between different tools, facilitating the interaction between different systems and applications. Finally, "Reusable" means that digital resources should be well-described for both humans and machines, in order to make it clear to both of them if a resource is relevant, if it can be reused and under what conditions, and who to credit for its reuse [7].

The FAIR principles are not intended to be a standard or a specification, but rather they are a guide for proper data management and stewardship. They are the following [6]:

- **To be Findable:**

- F1 (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- F2 data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
- F3 metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
- F4 (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

- **To be Accessible:**

- A1 (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
 - A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
 - A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
- A2 metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

- **To be Interoperable:**
 - I1 (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation
 - I2 (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
 - I3 (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data
- **To be Reusable:**
 - R1 meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
 - R1.1 (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
 - R1.2 (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
 - R1.3 (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

To enable the correct implementation of the FAIR data principles, appropriate tools must be used. For example, to make research data more FAIR, one possibility is to store the data and its related metadata together in a single file, rather than keeping them in separate files. This goal can be achieved by choosing appropriate formats for research data storage, such as the *HDF5* and *NeXus* formats, which are discussed in the following section [§2.2].

2.2 Formats for research data

To date, scientists around the world store their data in a variety of formats. Although using the same techniques, even similar facilities could use different formats. This fact has several drawbacks. For example, scientists working with multiple files in different formats must deal with file conversion to be able to integrate data having different origins, or data-analysis software must be able to manage several different formats. This behaviour is not compliant with the FAIR data principles, hence the development of a common format for research data that can serve as a standard is necessary.

In this context, the *HDF5* file format, and specifically the *NeXus* data format built on top of it, have emerged as possible solutions to this issue. The following subsections discuss these two formats.

2.2.1 HDF5 file format

HDF5 is an acronym for *Hierarchical Data Format version 5*. It is an open-source file format self-describing, and supporting large, complex, and het-

erogeneous data. It was originally developed at the *National Center for Supercomputing Applications* (NCSA) and is currently maintained by *The HDF group* [8].

Data within an HDF5 file are organized in a filesystem-like structure or, in other words, in a folders-and-subfolders-like hierarchical framework.

Different objects exist that can be defined in an HDF5 file [9]:

- groups
- datasets
- datatypes
- dataspace
- properties
- attributes

HDF5 groups can be seen as the analogues of folders in a filesystem. A group could contain other groups or HDF5 datasets, i.e. the analogues of filesystem files, which are the actual data contained in an HDF5 file. HDF5 files, groups and datasets can have associated metadata describing data itself. This is one of the main advantages of using HDF5 over other, less structured file formats. It makes HDF5 a self-describing format that contains all the necessary information to process the data, without requiring any external or additional metadata files.

Among metadata, HDF5 datatypes describe the individual data elements stored in a dataset. Datatypes include, for example, integer numbers, float numbers, and strings, enabling the HDF5 format to support really heterogeneous information.

HDF5 dataspace are objects that describe the shape of datasets. For example, datasets can have no elements (NULL dataspace), just one single element (scalar dataspace), or they can be an array with certain rank (e.g., 2 for a two-dimensional matrix) and dimensions (e.g., 10×10 for a matrix with 10 rows and 10 columns).

HDF5 properties are metadata describing characteristics or features of HDF5 objects. For example, an array of data stored in an HDF5 file can have the property to be contiguous, or chunked, and/or compressed. Finally, attributes store optional user metadata about the HDF5 object they are attached to. They are made of two components: a name, and the corresponding value. Furthermore, HDF5 supports links to connect objects and data.

One more advantage of HDF5 format is that it is a compressed format, which allow to optimize the overall file size, making it smaller. Moreover, the format supports *data slicing*, which allow to extract from a dataset only the portion of data needed for analysis, without having to read into the RAM the entire dataset, and enabling efficient management of large files.

2.2.2 NeXus data format

NeXus was born as an effort to define a common data exchange and archival format for neutron, X-ray and muon experiments [10]. It aims to define standards for both raw experimental data and processed data. NeXus history began in the mid-'90s [11], and to date its development is overseen by the *NeXus International Advisory Committee* (NIAC).

NeXus data format is based on the HDF5 file format, but it adds to HDF5 some domain-specific rules for organizing data within files, and a dictionary of well defined domain-specific field names. NeXus maintains the basic elements of the HDF5 format, such as groups, datasets (called *fields* in NeXus), attributes, and links. In NeXus, it is possible to add type information to a group, the so called NeXus class, and this is done via an HDF5 attribute. By convention, the prefix *NX* precedes each NeXus class name. For each class, the data format provides a set of terms (a dictionary) that can (but not have to) be used within that specific class, these dictionaries are named NeXus *base classes*. Anyway, it is possible to use other terms not included in base classes, but these terms might not be recognized by standard software.

The minimum set of groups and fields, and their organization in a NeXus file, which are needed (according to the NeXus community) to describe an application (e.g., a scientific technique or a specific instrument) is named NeXus *application definition*. Application definitions define standards within the NeXus community to save data and metadata for specific applications. Both application definitions and base classes are encoded in the *NeXus Definition Language* (NXDL). An NXDL file is an XML-based file that can be used to validate the structure of a NeXus data file.

Exactly as for the aforementioned HDF5 format, each NeXus group can contain other groups or fields. Attributes can be used to specify additional metadata describing the whole NeXus file or its groups and fields, while links can be used to represent the same information in different positions.

Each NeXus file is required to have at the top level one or more groups belonging to the NeXus base class *NXentry*. Each *NXentry* group contains all the data needed to describe an experimental run or scan, or a data processing. For example, it can contain groups belonging to base classes such as *NXsample*, *NXinstrument*, *NXdata*, which respectively describe the mea-

sured sample, the components of the instrument which has been used during a measurement, and the results obtained during an experiment or a data processing.

To date, the flexibility and efficiency of the NeXus data format have led to its adoption by several facilities around the world, such as SOLEIL (France), Diamond (UK), SINQ (Switzerland), KEK (Japan), and others [10, 12].

Its success and spread can also be attributed to the fact that the NeXus base classes and application definitions list is extensible. In order to add a new base class or application definition, the scientific community must submit a proposal which is initially added to NeXus as a *contributed definition*. Successively, after the revision and ratification conducted by the NIAC, the contributed definition can be accepted as a new base class or application definition.

Therefore, new application definitions — defining standards for techniques not yet considered by the community — can be introduced, enhancing NeXus spread and leading to its affirmation as a common standard in every scientific domain, thereby making the scientific process more FAIR.

For these reasons — within this thesis — NeXus was chosen as the standard for representing scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) data. However, an official application definition for STM does not yet exist. A solution to address this issue is presented in chapter 4.

2.3 Data management platforms

To date, a growing amount of research data and metadata are produced by researchers in all the scientific fields. Hence, it is of growing importance the development of methods and tools to safely store this huge amount of information, in such a way data and metadata can be easily shared, found, accessed, retrieved, and reused, not only by humans, but also by machines, that means to store data according to the FAIR principles [§2.1].

In this context, data management platforms have emerged as useful tools. Some examples are: the *MetaRepo* service by NFFA.eu; *Materials Cloud*, dedicated to computational materials science resources; and *NOMAD*, the FAIRmat data management platform for materials science.

In particular, the latter is compatible with the NeXus format — the standard chosen in this thesis for representing STM data — and constitutes a convenient tool for navigating metadata. Therefore, NOMAD proves to be a valuable platform within the framework of this thesis and, more generally, for the entire NFFA-DI project, which has adopted NOMAD as its reference data management platform for materials science.

2.3.1 NOMAD

NOMAD [13, 14] is a free and open-source platform for materials science data management, which has been developed by FAIRmat, an open NFDI (*Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur*) consortium. It provides a web service not only to archive, organize, analyse, share, and publish a user's own materials science data, but also to access and analyse data shared by other users.

Data in NOMAD is hierarchically structured and cross-referenced according to a schema which is called the *NOMAD Metainfo*. Indeed, NOMAD can extract machine-actionable data from more than 60 formats and codes (including the NeXus format), and its parsers automatically structure this data according to the NOMAD Metainfo schema. Moreover, thanks to the *NOMAD Remote Tools Hub* (NORTH), it is possible to run different tools to analyse data directly on NOMAD itself.

According to the FAIR guiding principles, data must be assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier in order to be findable. NOMAD also addresses this need. Indeed, it assigns a *DOI* (Digital Object Identifier) to each uploaded dataset, thereby uniquely and persistently identifying it on the web.

Moreover, the platform provides the option to install a local version of its software, which is named *NOMAD Oasis*. It allows users to get all the NOMAD features while implementing their own data policies and maintaining an high level of privacy. Furthermore, different NOMAD Oasis installations can be connected, for example, to enable inter-institutional data sharing.

Having all these features, NOMAD constitutes a powerful tool for the materials science community to address the challenge of making research data FAIR.

2.4 Electronic laboratory notebook

Due to the specificity of condensed matter physics experiments, the exploratory drive towards new methods for the synthesis and analysis of physical properties of samples, and the fact that these procedures — inevitably non-standardised — require significant human intervention, the data and metadata generated by measuring instruments and software are not the only information collected by researchers during an experiment. Indeed, a large amount of data and metadata is generated by researchers themselves, such as comments and observations on the ongoing experiment status, descriptions of experimental procedures followed before, during, and after a measurement,

annotations of incidental events occurring during an experiment, and more. Collecting all this information is fundamental to ensure the repeatability and reproducibility of experimental results, hence it is crucial to appropriately store this kind of data utilizing tools that ensure data is safely and long-term stored in a findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable form.

Until recently, such researcher-produced data and metadata were recorded by scientists in paper-based laboratory notebooks. However, this practice is no longer acceptable in the context of FAIR data principles. With the rise of digital technology, new helpful and FAIR-data-compliant tools have emerged, such as electronic laboratory notebooks, which are digital versions of their paper predecessors, and eLabFTW is one of them.

2.4.1 eLabFTW

eLabFTW [15] is a free and open-source electronic laboratory notebook, developed and maintained by the *Deltablot* company [16], and distributed in the form of a web application that can be installed, for example, on a research institution server. It is a multi-user platform that allows lab notebook pages to be shared with selected permissions among different users, thereby enabling collaboration.

eLabFTW pages are divided into two main sections: *experiments* and *resources*. *Experiments* function as traditional laboratory notebook pages, where users can record events occurring during experiments, along with their observations and comments. *Resources*, on the other hand, serve to list, organize, and describe items that are used in experiments — such as instruments, chemicals, procedures, and more.

eLabFTW assigns to each lab notebook page — whether it is an experiment or a resource — a unique identifier. Moreover, it supports the use of tags, categories, and customizable status indicators to label each page, as well as the use of links to interconnect different pages. In this way, users' data is made easily findable across the platform.

One of eLabFTW's features is the ability to create templates for lab notebook pages, allowing users to access ready-to-use page schemas.

Additionally, eLabFTW supports a variety of formats for exporting and importing data, thereby making the platform really flexible and interoperable.

Within this project, eLabFTW has been adopted as the reference electronic laboratory notebook to be used at the STRAS laboratory, with the aim of making the typical laboratory workflow more FAIR-compliant.

Chapter 3

Experimental context: surface science

The need for the development of new materials with new and innovative properties, together with the will to have a better understanding of the surrounding nature, have steered research interest in materials science toward nanomaterials and nanostructured systems. These kind of materials are characterized by at least one dimension and/or features with sizes on the order of nanometres (nm), which correspond to 1×10^{-9} m. When reaching such a small size, new properties arise in materials, like a modified reactivity or other peculiar electronic properties, due to the emergence of quantum effects. Among nanomaterials, one of the most famous is *graphene*: a single layer of carbon atoms which are arranged in an honeycomb network, that was isolated for the first time in 2004 [17].

Therefore, to date, the investigation of nanostructures is one of the core topics in materials science and, more specifically, in *surface science*, the branch of materials science which studies the properties of and phenomena occurring on top of material surfaces. Regarding this latter branch, one of the most direct ways for investigating a surface is to acquire an image of it to have a direct look at its appearance, that means working in the technical field of *microscopy*. However, a traditional optical microscope is not the appropriate instrument for nanostructured surface imaging. Indeed, due to the so-called *diffraction limit*, the minimum distance δ that can be resolved when using an optical microscope is limited by the light wavelength (λ) that is used to image the surface, according to the *Abbe criterion* [18]:

$$\delta = \frac{\lambda}{2 \cdot NA} \quad (3.1)$$

where NA is the so-called *numerical aperture* of the optical system, whose

value is typically on the order of unity.

This implies that when using visible light ($\lambda \sim 400 \text{ nm} \div 700 \text{ nm}$), the minimum resolvable distance is limited to hundreds of nanometres, which is not enough to resolve the nanometric features of a nanostructured system. Hence, there is a need for another kind of microscopy, not based on visible light, whose spatial resolution goes beyond the nanometre scale. The *Scanning Tunneling Microscopy* (STM) is a valid technique to address this issue. In the remainder of this thesis the acronym *STM* will be used to refer to both the technique and the corresponding instrument, the *Scanning Tunneling Microscope*. The context will clarify the meaning times by times.

This chapter first discusses the STM technique and its working principle. It then introduces the surface science STM laboratory — the STRAS laboratory — where this thesis work was conducted. Finally, it describes the workflow routinely carried out in this laboratory for a typical experiment. In particular, this last part is fundamental for understanding how researchers routinely work in the laboratory, which problems they might encounter during an experiment, and the quantity and type of data and metadata they need to record. Such knowledge is essential — and cannot be ignored — for a data curator aiming to design an appropriate FAIR-by-design workflow that aligns with the researchers' needs.

3.1 STM and its working principle

Gerd Binnig and Heinrich Rohrer published the first STM results in 1982 [19]. However, they gained the interest of the scientific community only in 1983 when they atomically imaged with STM the 7×7 reconstruction of the Si(111) surface, a challenge that, before them, was considered one of the most intriguing in surface science [20]. Thanks to these results they won the Nobel prize in 1986.

The STM working principle can be described as follows [fig. 3.1]. The microscope is equipped with a metallic tip, typically made of tungsten, which is atomically sharp, indeed its apex is ideally single-atom-terminated. Such a tip constitutes the STM probe. The tip is approached to a conductive sample, that is the target of the scientific investigation, and their distance is reduced down to a few nanometres. Anyway, tip and sample are never in contact. Successively, a voltage bias is applied between tip and sample, and then electrons start flowing between the two electrodes, generating an electric current. It should be noted that such a current flows even if tip and sample are not in physical contact. This happens due to the quantum effect named *quantum tunnelling*, and the electric current is said to be the *tunnelling*

current. The tunneling current (I_T) depends mainly on two factors: the distance between tip and sample, and the densities of electronic states on both the probe and the small surface area above which the tip is located. More specifically, the dependence from the distance (d) is exponential, and can be approximated as follow [21]:

$$I_T \sim \exp(-2kd) \quad (3.2)$$

with a decay constant $k \sim 1 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ ($1 \text{ \AA} = 1 \text{ \AA} = 1 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}$). Hence, even a few ångströms change in the tip-surface distance can induce a significant change in the tunneling current.

The second current dependence is the one on the electronic densities of states, or DOS. It implies that the tunnelling current depends on the local chemistry of the sample surface, i.e. on surface's local electronic environment, apart from the chemistry of the tip apex. This means that different atomic chemical species on the surface, which are located just below the STM tip, can induce different tunneling current intensities.

Once a tunnelling current is established, the tip is raster-scanned over the sample surface via a system of piezoelectric motors, a set of motors made of a peculiar material which can contract or expand when an appropriate electric field is applied to it. In such a way, the value of the tunnelling current is collected point by point on the sample surface, while it changes accordingly with the tip-surface distance and the local chemical environment of the surface. Indeed, even while scanning a macroscopically flat sample surface, it can happen that the tip encounters a group of clustered atoms sitting on top of the surface, or it can interact with an atomically high step, thereby changing the tip-surface distance. Moreover, the tip can interact with superficial atoms belonging to different chemical species or with atoms of the same type, but arranged in different configurations, thereby having different electronic environments.

The tunnelling current values collected at each point of the investigated surface are the basis for the STM image generation. Indeed, an STM can image a surface using two different modes: *constant height mode* and *constant current mode* [fig. 3.2].

Acquiring an image in constant height mode means that the STM tip is scanned across the sample surface, the tunnelling current is collected point by point (or pixel by pixel) into a two-dimensional (2D) array, and this array is then plotted as a colour-coded map of the surface.

Alternatively, STM can image a surface in constant current mode, which is the most common mode. In this mode, while the STM tip is scanned across the sample surface, the tunnelling current is kept constant. This is

Figure 3.1: Working principle of the scanning tunnelling microscope. A metallic tip and a conductive sample are brought close to each other, and a voltage bias V is applied between them, while the tip is raster-scanned over the sample surface. The inset shows a detail of the tip–surface system, with two chemically different atomic species (pink and light-blue spheres) sitting on top of the surface (for this reason, they are also called *adatoms*). Due to the applied voltage bias V , electrons (e^- , shown in green) tunnel between the tip and the sample, thereby generating an electric current. This tunnelling current — whose intensity profile is depicted as a sinusoidal curve — varies according to the surface topography and the local electronic density of states (DOS), i.e., the local chemical environment.

made possible by a feedback loop that reads the tunnelling current and, if it changes relative to a fixed set-point value, sends a signal to a piezoelectric motor system that adjusts the tip-surface distance to bring the current back to its set-point value. In this way, the tip position along the direction perpendicular to the sample surface is adjusted point by point to follow the surface topography and DOS profiles. Hence, in constant current mode, this tip position is collected pixel by pixel and stored in a 2D array. Then, as in constant height mode, this array is plotted as a colour-coded map of the surface.

Regardless of which mode is used to acquire an STM image, care must be taken in its interpretation. As previously mentioned, an STM image reflects not only the surface topography (i.e., the degree of surface roughness) but also the local electronic density of states. Therefore, while scanning in constant height mode, for example, an increase in the tunnelling current may result either from a reduced tip-surface distance or from an increased local DOS.

Figure 3.2: Schematic representation of the two STM scanning modes: **(a)** constant height mode, and **(b)** constant current mode. The image is taken from [22].

3.2 The STRAS laboratory

The current thesis work was conducted at the STRAS (*Surface sStructure and Reactivity at the Atomic Scale*) laboratory, a CNR-IOM (*Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche - Istituto Officina dei Materiali*) laboratory, located at the Basovizza campus of *Area Science Park* in Trieste, Italy [23].

The laboratory aims to investigate the structural and electronic properties of solid surfaces at the nanoscale, with a focus on their evolution during surface processes. This goal is achieved through a variety of instruments and techniques available at the STRAS laboratory, including scanning tunnelling microscopy. Indeed, the laboratory is equipped with two scanning tunnelling microscopes: an Omicron variable temperature STM (VT-STM), which operates in the temperature range of 140 K to 900 K; and an Omicron low temperature STM (LT-STM), which can operate at 77 K or 4 K, depending on the cryogenic liquid used for cooling — liquid nitrogen (LN_2) or liquid helium (LHe), respectively.

In recent years, one of the main research topics addressed at STRAS has been the growth of carbon-based two-dimensional (2D) layers and the investigation of their properties and reactivity. In particular, significant attention has been devoted to the study of graphene, both pristine and doped with heteroatoms — such as nitrogen (N), boron (B), and transition metals (TM) — as well as to the reactivity of these systems toward toxic and/or greenhouse gases, such as carbon oxides (CO , CO_2). Understanding the practices and typical workflows routinely carried out by scientists is pivotal to appropriately *FAIR-ify* a laboratory. Hence, the following section [§3.2.1] discusses a typical workflow for the preparation and properties investigation of graphene-based 2D systems at the STRAS laboratory.

3.2.1 A model surface science laboratory workflow

This section describes the typical workflow routinely carried out at the STRAS laboratory for the synthesis and properties characterization of heteroatom-doped (e.g., N-, B-, TM-doped) graphene.

Initially, a clean, polished and flat slab of a metallic material (e.g., nickel, Ni) is chosen as a substrate for the synthesis of graphene, such a substrate constitutes a support for graphene itself. The substrate is loaded into a primary *ultra-high vacuum* (UHV, pressure lower than 1×10^{-9} mbar) chamber — which is connected to the STM UHV chamber through a valve — for the substrate’s surface further cleaning and graphene growth. UHV is a required condition for the synthesis and, in general, for the entire experiment, as it allows for a controlled atmosphere inside the experimental chamber. This helps to limit undesired contamination during graphene growth and reduces the deposition — or, technically speaking, adsorption — of atmospheric molecules on the graphene surface during measurements, thereby ensuring a relatively long period of surface cleanliness. Hence, it is essential for a scientist to monitor and record the chamber pressure values in a laboratory notebook to make the interpretation of the experimental results clearer, and to ensure the repeatability and reproducibility of the experiment.

Once the substrate is loaded into the primary UHV chamber, its surface is further cleaned through several cycles of two alternating procedures: argon ion (Ar^+) *sputtering* and high-temperature *annealing*.

During sputtering, argon gas is introduced into the experimental chamber, where the Ar atoms are ionized into Ar^+ . These ions are then accelerated toward the sample surface by an applied voltage on the order of kV. This procedure aims to bombard the surface with inert gas ions, physically removing undesired molecules and atoms deposited on the surface.

After sputtering, the sample undergoes annealing. During this procedure, the sample is heated to several hundred degrees Celsius ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at a precisely controlled rate. The final temperature reached depends on the substrate material. The substrate is then maintained at this temperature for several dozen minutes, after which it is cooled down to room temperature at a carefully controlled rate. Annealing aims to clean the sample surface by causing all adsorbed species to desorb from the substrate. Additionally, it allows the metal atoms in the top few layers of the substrate to rearrange into a more stable energetic configuration, resulting in a more ordered and flatter surface. As with a Ni substrate, this procedure is also relevant for graphene layer doping [24, 25]. Indeed, if the substrate’s bulk is contaminated with heteroatoms, such as nitrogen or boron, the maximum annealing temperature, along with the heating and cooling rates, determines the amount of heteroatoms that

migrate from the bulk to the substrate's surface. These surface-segregated heteroatoms can then substitute carbon (C) atoms in the graphene lattice during synthesis, thereby doping the graphene layer. Therefore, it should now be clear that recording all parameters related to sputtering and annealing in a laboratory notebook, in a clear and understandable manner, is one of the key responsibilities a researcher must fulfil to ensure the repeatability and reproducibility of sample preparation.

Once the substrate surface is cleaned, graphene growth can begin. At the STRAS laboratory, this is carried out using a method called *chemical vapor deposition* (CVD). In CVD, the metallic substrate is heated to a temperature in the range of 500 °C to 600 °C, and exposed to a partial pressure of a gaseous hydrocarbon — at STRAS, ethylene (C₂H₄) is used — typically in the range of 1×10^{-7} mbar to 1×10^{-6} mbar. The system is usually maintained under these conditions for a period of 1 h to 1.5 h, during which the hydrocarbon molecules that reach the hot substrate surface undergo thermal cracking, leaving behind carbon (C) atoms that crystallize into the graphene lattice, while hydrogen (H₂) desorbs. During this process, if the substrate was previously contaminated with heteroatoms — as mentioned earlier — some of these atoms can become incorporated into the graphene lattice, thereby doping the graphene layer. After this exposure phase, the gaseous hydrocarbon is evacuated from the experimental chamber, but the sample is kept at the high growth temperature for an additional 10 min. Finally, the sample is cooled down to room temperature at a controlled cooling rate. As with the sputtering and annealing procedures, parameters such as the heating and cooling rates, the maximum graphene growth temperature, the hydrocarbon partial pressure, the exposure duration, and the post-exposure time before sample cooling all play a crucial role in determining the quality and doping level of the synthesized graphene layer. Therefore, all of these parameters must be accurately recorded by the researcher in the laboratory notebook.

At this stage of the experiment, the graphene sample is ready and can be transferred to the STM for imaging and analysis. At STRAS, particular interest is devoted to the sample's reactivity toward gases such as CO and CO₂. Therefore, *operando* or *in situ* gas exposure experiments may be performed, and once again, the gas partial pressure and exposure duration must be carefully recorded by the researchers. However, regardless of whether a reactivity test is performed, STM images of the surface are acquired and saved — along with all relevant instrument metadata — by the acquisition software, using a file format that depends on the microscope's electronics producer. In the case of the VT-STM, this file format is *sm4*, which is a proprietary format.

At the end of this section, it should be clear how much data and metadata

are collected — not only automatically by the acquisition software, but also, and especially, manually by researchers in the laboratory notebook. Moreover, it must be taken into account that when conducting an experiment such as the one described, many unexpected events may occur — e.g., a pressure burst, a broken heating filament, and more — and all such occurrences must also be recorded in the laboratory notebook to ensure a clear and complete history of the sample and the entire experimental process. Therefore, it is essential to design and implement a FAIR-by-design workflow that enables researchers to safely store all their data and metadata — without forgetting any — in a way that is easily findable, accessible, understandable, standardized, and machine-actionable. A few proposals to achieve this goal are presented in the following chapter [§4].

Chapter 4

An STM laboratory FAIR-ification

Chapter 2 discussed the importance of making scientific research and its products FAIR, while chapter 3 introduced the STM technique and the typical workflow at the STRAS laboratory.

The present chapter serves as a meeting point between the two previous chapters. In particular, it discusses several solutions that were designed and implemented during this thesis work to make the STRAS laboratory more compliant with FAIR data principles.

First, it presents a suggested workflow in eLabFTW for STRAS researchers conducting experiments, aimed at better organizing their metadata — especially that related to sample preparation. Second, the chapter introduces a *graphical user interface* (GUI), developed in Python during this thesis, which enables the automation — and thus the standardization — of certain routine tasks performed by the STRAS staff. Finally, the chapter introduces a proposed NeXus application definition for STM and discusses the mapping of metadata extracted from STRAS’s VT-STM to this metadata schema.

4.1 Design of a workflow in eLabFTW

The previous chapter [§3.2.1] described the typical experimental workflow at the STRAS laboratory and showed how vast is the amount of data and metadata that researchers need to collect and safely store to ensure a correct interpretation of the experimental results, along with the experiment repeatability and reproducibility. Hence, the development of a FAIR-by-design approach to manage all this information is of fundamental importance.

With such a goal in mind, during this thesis work, a workflow in eLabFTW

was designed and implemented to enable researchers to organize and easily find their data.

First of all, it was necessary to transition from an old, locally installed electronic lab notebook — which had already been in use in the laboratory — to the new online platform, eLabFTW. For the laboratory, this already represents an improvement in data management, thanks to the ability to access the lab notebook from anywhere — even from home, supporting remote work — as well as the capability to share notebook pages with colleagues, facilitating collaboration.

To distinguish among lab notebook pages related to experiments conducted on the different experimental setups located at the STRAS laboratory, the eLabFTW *status* label has been chosen as an indicator of the experimental system used. For example, VT and LT statuses were created to label experiments conducted on the VT-STM and LT-STM, respectively. In this way, a researcher looking for the complete list of experiments conducted on the VT-STM can simply filter by status and quickly obtain an overview of all the corresponding lab notebook pages.

Therefore, when starting a new experiment, a researcher should first create a new eLabFTW experiment page, assign the status corresponding to the setup they intend to use, and then begin filling in the notebook page with information related to the experiment.

One of the fields that a researcher must fill in on an eLabFTW experiment page is the page *title*. A title convention has been adopted in which each title consists of two parts separated by a dash: a date in the format YYYY.MM.DD, and a brief description (a few words) of the experiment recorded on that page. In this way, researchers can quickly get an idea of the content of a lab notebook page and when the experiment was conducted, just by looking at the title.

Thorough information about the experiment must be reported by researchers in the main text body of the eLabFTW page. First, researchers must record the experiment starting time and the internal pressure of the experimental chamber at the beginning of the experiment. Then, they can proceed to take notes on the substrate chosen for the experiment, as well as the cleaning and graphene growth procedures. To help scientists record all this information — without forgetting anything — templates have been designed in eLabFTW that include all the necessary parameters. Accordingly, a standardized vocabulary, a specific ordered structure, and a consistent text formatting style have been adopted. Indeed, one of the main challenges in using a text field — such as the one eLabFTW provides for recording data and metadata — is that it gives users excessive freedom in writing. As a result, there is a risk of omitting parameters or having different users employing dif-

ferent vocabularies or formatting styles, thereby reducing the completeness, overall clarity, and machine-actionability of the entries in the lab notebook. Therefore, the designed templates aim to address these issues.

Once sample preparation is complete (e.g., after substrate cleaning and graphene growth) and the sample is ready for measurement, a unique name must be assigned to it. The naming convention adopted is the same one that was previously in use at STRAS. According to this convention, a sample name consists of three parts: an abbreviation, such as *VT* or *LT*, denoting the setup in which the sample was produced (VT-STM or LT-STM, respectively); a date in the YYMMDD format, indicating when the sample was created; and, separated by an underscore, an alphanumeric code such as *A1*, denoting the version of the sample.

To better understand the last component of the naming convention:

- The numeric part (e.g., the “1” in *A1*) is incremented when the sample undergoes minor modifications.
- The alphabetic part (e.g., the “A” in *A1*) is incremented only when an old sample is discarded and a new one is created from scratch.

For example, if a sample named *VT250101_A1* is exposed to CO gas as part of an adsorption study, the resulting sample (i.e., *VT250101_A1* with CO molecules adsorbed on top) is considered a new version and is named *VT250101_A2*. If this new sample is later cleaned through sputtering and annealing, removing all species deposited on the surface, and a new graphene layer is then grown on the clean substrate, the resulting sample is assigned the name *VT250101_B1*, with the alphabetic part incremented and the numeric part reset.

Since the same sample may be measured in different setups or referred to on multiple eLabFTW pages, a dedicated eLabFTW page must be assigned to it. To facilitate this, a *sample* category has been created in the eLabFTW resources section. Therefore, a researcher who creates a sample must duplicate all relevant information about the sample and its preparation on a new resource page within the sample category, titled with the sample’s name. In this way, all information related to a specific sample is consolidated into a single lab notebook page. One of the advantages of this approach is that eLabFTW automatically assigns a unique, persistent identifier (ID) to each page. As a result, creating a sample resource page will assign a unique ID to the sample, unequivocally identifying it. At this point, it is both possible and necessary to link the newly created sample resource to all eLabFTW pages containing experiments related to that sample, as well as to other sample resources derived from it. This process ensures that a comprehensive history

of the sample's lifecycle is documented, accessible, and centralized on the specific sample resource page.

Similar to samples, a category for substrates has been created in the eLabFTW resources section, with the same purpose as the *sample* category. In fact, the same substrate may be used as a support in several sample preparations. Therefore, having a dedicated resource page for each substrate, which can be linked to all experiments and samples associated with it, is essential for a researcher to clearly identify the substrate and access its complete history.

In addition to the sample and substrate categories, other resource categories (e.g., *STM tip*, *Pump*, *Evaporator*, and more) have been created to represent, describe, identify, and track the history of all the equipment used in the experimental apparatuses at the STRAS laboratory. This ensures that each tool in the STRAS laboratory has its own dedicated eLabFTW page, complete with a unique persistent identifier, creating a comprehensive and easily accessible documentation system for all laboratory researchers.

A researcher creating a new eLabFTW page — whether for an experiment or a resource — must assign appropriate *tags* to it. This allows users to filter eLabFTW pages by specific tags, making it easier and faster to locate content related to particular topics.

For example, several tags have already been created, such as:

- *daily*, to denote routine tasks;
- *graphene*, to indicate the presence of graphene on a studied sample;
- *cleaning*, to mark that a cleaning procedure was performed;
- *Au111*, to specify the use of a gold substrate with (111) crystallographic orientation.

Finally, at STRAS, a researcher conducting STM measurements may acquire numerous surface images of a sample in a single day. All these images should be uploaded and attached — along with the corresponding filenames — in sequence within the main text body of the relevant eLabFTW experiment page. This process is essential not only for fully documenting the experiment by linking the experimental data to the lab notebook, but also for providing scientists with a quick and clear overview of the acquired STM images.

However, this task can be lengthy and tedious, as the number of images acquired in a single day can reach into the hundreds. Additionally, in cases such as the VT-STM, the files generated by the software are in the *sm4*

format. STM data in this format must be opened and processed using specialized software tools (e.g., Gwyddion) to enable proper and user-friendly visualization of the images. As a result, researchers are required to process and upload each STM image to the eLabFTW experiment page one by one, which is time-consuming.

To address this issue by automating the task and easing the workload for STRAS staff, a GUI (*graphical user interface*) was developed during this thesis work. The tool is presented in the following section [§4.2].

4.2 A GUI for STM users to interface with eLabFW

As anticipated in the previous section [§4.1], a Python-based graphical user interface (GUI) was developed during this thesis work to support the STRAS staff in their daily tasks. This GUI, named *Meerkat*, is built upon pre-existing software originally developed by Dr. Mirco Panighel — a former STRAS researcher whom I would like to acknowledge for his contribution. In this thesis, his version has been expanded and specifically adapted to enable integration with eLabFTW.

As mentioned in §4.1, STRAS researchers working with scanning tunneling microscopy may acquire hundreds of STM images in a single day. These images must then be processed and uploaded to eLabFTW one by one — a task that can be extremely time-consuming. Meerkat provides researchers with a convenient interface to streamline this process for the VT-STM setup. It leverages the Python package *spym* [26] to automatically open and perform preliminary processing on *sm4* files generated by the VT-STM software. This processing includes row alignment, plane subtraction to correct for image tilting, and data offset adjustment to shift the minimum data value to zero. Subsequently, using application programming interfaces (APIs) for eLabFTW — some of which were shared through the kind assistance of Dr. Marco Prenassi, who must be acknowledged — the processed STM images, converted into *png* format, are automatically uploaded and attached to the corresponding eLabFTW experiment page, as identified by a unique page ID provided by the user [fig. 4.1]. This automation significantly reduces the time and effort required by researchers, greatly enhancing efficiency in their workflow.

Another feature of Meerkat — currently still under development — is an interface for annotating all metadata relevant to a sample’s description and preparation [fig. 4.2].

Meerkat provides users with a customizable form that researchers must fill out during sample preparation. In this form, users are required to annotate sample identity metadata — such as the sample’s name, creation date, and parent sample — as well as structural and compositional details, including the supporting substrate and the layer structure. The form also allows for annotation of the substrate cleaning procedure, with all associated parameters, along with those used for graphene synthesis and/or gas exposure processes.

Once completed, all provided information is saved in a *JSON* file — an open, machine-readable format — named according to the sample’s name. This allows for the creation of a structured and easily parsable catalogue of all samples prepared and studied at the STRAS laboratory. In the future, this catalogue could be readily converted into other standardized formats, such as NeXus.

Furthermore, Meerkat enables users to automatically create a sample resource page in eLabFTW using the metadata from the form. In this way, a unique ID in eLabFTW is attributed to the newly created sample. The tool automatically assigns appropriate tags to the resource, and ensures consistency in data recording. A feature currently under development will also allow this sample resource page to be automatically linked to a relevant experiment page.

This feature of Meerkat — offering a well-structured, consistent metadata schema with a fixed vocabulary for sample-related entries — is intended as an alternative to eLabFTW templates to address eLabFTW’s issue of inconsistent data recording among different users discussed in §4.1.

It should be noted that the terms used by this Meerkat tool to describe the sample and its preparation are based on a vocabulary already in use at the STRAS laboratory. However, this vocabulary is an in-house one, lacking official status at a global level; therefore, it is not FAIR-compliant. Hence, in a future update of Meerkat, a new, officially recognized vocabulary must be adopted, with terms globally unambiguously identified via persistent identifiers. This can be achieved through the use of appropriate ontologies — collections of terms, along with their interrelations, within a specific domain. An example is the *Chemical Methods Ontology* (CHMO) for the chemical domain.

Meerkat inherits from the software previously developed by Dr. Panighel the capability to interact with the VT-STM acquisition software associated with RHK’s *R9plus* electronics [fig. 4.1]. Specifically, it enables the automatic initialization of the image-saving path within the acquisition software, generating directory paths based on the sample name and the date on which the measurements are performed. This ensures that all acquired images are

Figure 4.1: Main window of Meerkat, showing the section used to interact with the VT-STM acquisition software associated with RHK’s *R9plus* electronics, as well as the section for updating an eLabFTW experiment page (identified by a specific ID) with STM images from a designated data folder.

consistently stored within a structured hierarchy of folders and subfolders organized by date.

To further assist researchers by enabling quick and convenient visualization of STM images alongside their corresponding metadata, Meerkat includes an image gallery feature. This tool allows users to navigate through STM data folders, displaying previews of STM images alongside the associated metadata extracted from the *sm4* files [fig. 4.3].

The metadata is retrieved using the Python package *spym*, and includes all scanning tunneling microscope parameter values used during the acquisition of each specific STM image. Meerkat also saves this metadata in a JSON file, creating documentation that is both human- and machine-readable, and that may be readily converted into more convenient formats, such as NeXus, by mapping it into an STM application definition schema — as discussed in the following section [§4.3].

The source code of Meerkat can be found in the CNR-IOM section of the MDMC official GitHub repository [27].

The screenshot shows a web application window titled "Create New Sample". At the top, there are four tabs: "General properties", "Cleaning", "Graphene growth", and "Gas exposure". The "General properties" tab is active. Below the tabs, there are two main sections, each with a checked checkbox and a title:

- Sample ID**: Contains a "Parent sample" dropdown menu, an "Add entry" button, a "Sample name" text input field with the placeholder "Enter value", a "Creation date" text input field with the placeholder "e.g., 2025-04-24", and a "Parent sample" text input field with the placeholder "Enter value" and a red "x" delete button.
- Sample composition/structure**: Contains a "Layer" dropdown menu, an "Add entry" button, a "Substrate" text input field with the placeholder "Enter value" and a red "x" delete button, a "Layer 1" text input field with the placeholder "Enter value" and a red "x" delete button, and a "Layer 2" text input field with the placeholder "Enter value" and a red "x" delete button. To the right of these fields are a blue square icon and another red "x" delete button.

At the bottom of the form, there is a "Sample composition/structure" dropdown menu, an "Add subsection" button, a "New section" button, and a large green "Save" button.

Figure 4.2: One of the panels in Meerkat’s form for collecting metadata related to sample description and preparation.

Figure 4.3: Meerkat’s gallery tool for visualizing STM images alongside their corresponding metadata.

4.3 Mapping STM data to a metadata schema

Chapter 2 discussed the NeXus format and presented it as a convenient format for storing data in compliance with FAIR data principles. Indeed, this format is also convenient for uploading data to the NOMAD platform, which — within the present project — has been chosen as the data management platform for storing materials science research data.

Therefore, it would be useful to convert STM files generated at the STRAS laboratory into the NeXus format. To do so, a NeXus application definition for STM is necessary; however, an official release has not yet been distributed by the NIAC.

A solution to this issue has been proposed by the FAIRmat consortium, the same group behind the development of NOMAD. FAIRmat introduced a proposal for an STM application definition, which they named *NXstm* [28]. Therefore, after careful evaluation of this option and the possibility of developing an in-house schema, FAIRmat’s proposal has been selected — within the scope of the present project — as the STM metadata schema to comply with for converting STM files at STRAS. Consequently, during this thesis work, VT-STM metadata was retrieved from the *sm4* files using the aforementioned Python package *spym*, and the extracted variables were mapped onto the *NXstm* schema.

This work has not been straightforward due to the imperfect one-to-one correspondence between the NXstm fields and the variables extracted from the *sm4* file. For example, the *scan_mode* field in NXstm — which admits *constant height* or *constant current* as possible values — must be filled in according to the boolean value of the *sm4* variable *feedback_active*. If *feedback_active* is *true*, then the *scan_mode* value must be *constant current*; if *feedback_active* is *false*, then the *scan_mode* value must be *constant height*.

Other examples include the NXstm *scan_range_x* or *forward_speed_x* fields. The former field — which describes the length of the image along the x-direction — can be obtained by multiplying the two *sm4* variables *RHK_Xsize* and *RHK_Xscale*, which represent the number of pixels along the x-direction and the length corresponding to each pixel, respectively. In contrast, the *forward_speed_x* — which describes the speed of the tip while scanning, for example, in the positive x-direction — can be obtained by dividing the *sm4* variable *RHK_Xscale* by the *sm4* variable *time_per_point*, which represents the time required for the tip to move from one pixel to the next.

As previously mentioned, the present thesis was conducted within the framework of the NFFA-DI project, which includes among its goals the aim of making several CNR-IOM laboratories — including STRAS — FAIR-compliant. To support this objective, a third-party software development company named *Mashfrog* was hired. Mashfrog is responsible for the digital transformation of STRAS and all other CNR-IOM laboratories involved.

Hence, once the metadata mapping was completed, it was shared with Mashfrog for integration into the overall FAIR-by-design project system. Mashfrog is currently working on interconnecting all digital and analogue devices at STRAS and will handle the automatic conversion of VT-STM data into NeXus format, based on the provided mapping.

Once the entire system is online, the STRAS laboratory will also be able to upload complete, metadata-rich STM NeXus files to NOMAD in a convenient and standardized manner.

Chapter 5

Conclusion and outlooks

The chapters presented in this thesis discussed how modern scientific research is moving toward producing more and more data and metadata. This vast amount of information to be managed no longer permits the use of traditional data management methods and tools. Hence, it is necessary to adopt new practices and tools that allow for the appropriate management of all these data and metadata, making them findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable — i.e., *FAIR*.

In this context, several convenient tools can be chosen, including: the NeXus data format, a flexible and open-source format built on top of the HDF5 standard, which allows for organizing metadata-rich research data in a hierarchical structure; NOMAD, a free and open-source materials science data management platform for storing, sharing, and processing research data; and electronic laboratory notebooks, such as eLabFTW, which are used to annotate, safely store, easily find and access, interconnect, and share research metadata.

The aim of this thesis was to initiate the *FAIR-ification* process in a CNR-IOM STM laboratory — the STRAS laboratory, in Trieste, Italy — meaning to make the laboratory more compliant with the guidelines dictated by the FAIR data principles.

First, a workflow in eLabFTW was designed to serve as a guide for STRAS researchers on how to correctly use eLabFTW for organizing research data and metadata. A possible use of some eLabFTW features — such as *experiments* and *resources* sections, the *status* label, templates, *categories*, *tags*, and *links* — was suggested to make metadata complete, clear, easily findable, and interconnected. In particular, the creation of an item within a *sample* category in the eLabFTW resources section, for collecting all relevant information about a specific studied sample, is strongly recommended. In this way, a persistent identifier (ID) — unique within eLabFTW — is attributed

to the resource instance, unequivocally identifying that sample. Moreover, by linking this resource to other related resources and experiments, a complete history of the sample's lifecycle is reconstructed and collected on a single eLabFTW page, creating documentation accessible to all researchers.

Second, to meet the needs of the STRAS staff — by accelerating, automating, and standardizing the execution of certain tasks — a Python-based GUI, named *Meerkat*, was developed. It supports users by preliminarily processing *sm4* files acquired at STRAS and uploading the resulting STM images to the corresponding eLabFTW experiment page; by providing a tool for consistently creating a *sample* resource in eLabFTW, complete with all necessary sample-related metadata and tags; and by offering a convenient tool for visualizing STM images alongside their metadata.

Finally, in order to convert the *sm4* files produced at STRAS into the more convenient and FAIR-compliant NeXus format, a suitable STM application definition was sought. After careful evaluation, the *NXstm* schema proposed by FAIRmat was selected. Subsequently, the metadata extracted from the *sm4* files was mapped onto this schema.

Despite the work accomplished in this thesis, the FAIR-ification process at STRAS is not yet complete, and further efforts are needed to ensure that the laboratory and the research conducted there are fully FAIR-compliant.

The workflow in eLabFTW can be further refined, and the Meerkat software can be upgraded. Regarding the latter, the capability to automatically link a sample resource page to a related experiment page is currently under development. Moreover, the adoption of an ontology-based vocabulary is planned for a future Meerkat update to make the terms used globally and unambiguously understandable, thereby improving software interoperability. Additionally, a future feature planned for implementation is the ability to create a sample NeXus file from the metadata provided by users in Meerkat, which can then be linked to STM NeXus files associated with a specific measured specimen. In this way, different STM NeXus files containing measurements related to the same sample can be connected to a single sample file, which contains all the information needed to identify and describe the sample. This approach avoids redundancies in the STM NeXus files themselves and helps create a well-structured and organized sample library.

Additionally, the *sm4* metadata mapping onto the *NXstm* schema has already been submitted to *Mashfrog*, the company responsible for the digital transformation of the STRAS laboratory. They are handling the automatic conversion of *sm4* files into NeXus according to the submitted mapping. Therefore, in the near future, the STRAS laboratory will be able to produce STM data in the FAIR-data-compliant NeXus format, which can be easily uploaded to the selected materials science data management platform

NOMAD.

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